

Description of scurvy by Kramer (1720,1737)

Summary by James Lind (1772)

This is James Lind's English summary of a text on scurvy by Kramer in 1737, the original was published in Latin.

J. G. H. Kramer, physician to the Imperial army in Hungary
<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7fpbavt/items?canvas=574>

Yellow is used to indicate sections describing the symptoms of scurvy.

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James Lind's comments on Kramer:

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What were the sentiments of a most judicious physician, may be seen by looking into *Sydenham*; what were the dreadful consequences of such writings, will appear by looking into **Kramer**: but how many unhappy patients must have suffered in this disease before the slaughter of thousands at a time (Kramer) began to open the eyes of mankind, is too melancholy a subject to dwell upon!

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/16/mode/2up>

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... Mercury may be reputed a poison in the scurvy; **Kramer** gives an account of 400 men destroyed by it; yet *Boerhaave* recommends it...

To so great an authority, which, as far as is consistent with truth and the good of mankind, I shall always respect, may be opposed a much greater, viz. the experience of a physician who had the greatest opportunity perhaps any one ever had, of being conversant with scorbutic patients; woful experience gained by being witness to the death of many thousands, when *Boerhaave's Aphorisms* on this subject were of no use to him... Kramer epistol. p. 27, 28.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/24/mode/2up>

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Moreover, the sea-scurvy is called by several authors *the Dutch distemper*; especially by the celebrated *Francis Gemelli Careri*, who has wrote the best voyages in the *Italian* language. The *French* formerly gave it the name of the land evil. And indeed the symptoms of the mady are at this day uniform and the same, both at sea and land; in *Holland, Greenland, Hungary (Kramer), Cronstadt, Wiburgh (Nitzsch), Scotland (Grainger), &c.* which sufficiently evinces the absurdity of the assertion advanced by several authors, that since the first accounts of it were published, the face and appearances of the calamity have been greatly changed.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/30/mode/2up>

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...

But a heavier charge lies against them. When the true scurvy does really occur, their writings, so far from being useful, are rather hurtful to practitioners; which I think needs no farther proof, than **Kramer's** letter to the college of physicians at *Vienna*. Their doctrines have perverted the judgment of even some of the best writers.

...

The cure of scorbutic diseases contracted either at land or sea, is entirely the same. This will appear to any person who peruses *Backstrom's* and *Kramer's* observations, and several other histories related in this treatise.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/32/mode/2up>

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It has a most fatal influence on the practice. Thus the original and real disease has been lost and confounded amidst such indefinite distinctions and divisions of it, that it is sometimes not known by the best practitioners, when it really occurs. *To this was owing the loss of so many thousand Germans in Hungary (Kramer), not many years ago, where the physicians to that army, together with the whole learned college of physicians at Vienna, assisted by all the books extant on the Subject, were at a loss how to remedy this dreadful calamity.* And for this reason many unhappy people are daily injudiciously treated at land, as must have been observed by every one acquainted with the distemper. Thence likewise pernicious methods have been recommended at sea, and too often put in practice.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/40/mode/2up>

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Thus, when it lately raged with such a remarkable devastation among the *Germans in Hungary*, the physician to that army (**Kramer**) was surprised to find that not one officer, even the most subaltern, received the infection.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/42/mode/2up>

p.44-45

Thus, where the causes productive of it are general, and violent in a high degree, it becomes an *epidemic* or universal calamity, and rages with great and diffusive virulence: as happens often to seamen in long voyages; sometimes to armies (Nitzsch), very lately to the *German* soldiers in *Hungary* (**Kramer**); frequently to troops when closely besieged, as to the *Saxon* garrison in *Thorn* (Bachstrom), the besieged in *Breda* (Vander Mye), in *Rochelle*, as also *Stetin*: and at other times to whole countries; as in *Brabant*, in the year 1556; and in *Holland*, ann. 1562.
<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/44/mode/2up>

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That salt meats have sometimes no share in occasioning this disease, is demonstrable from the many *Germans* in *Hungary* destroyed by it, who eat neither salt beef nor pork; on the contrary, they had fresh beef at a very low price. Vid. **Krameri** *epist.* p. 33.
<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/48/mode/2up>

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This disease is not indeed peculiar to the ocean, there being many instances of its raging with equal violence at land (Vid. the case of the *German* troops in *Hungary*: **Kramer** etc.).
<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/60/mode/2up>

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In *Hungary*, where there must have been the strongest disposition in the air to produce the scurvy (Vid. **Kramer**), not only the officers, and natives of the country, but even the dragoons¹, by having more pay, and consequently better diet, cloathing, and lodging, though equally subject to the other diseases of the country, yet kept free from the scurvy. Who were attacked by it? Only the *Bohemians*, who eat the coarsest and most indigestible food. The *Bohemians* used no other than what was the ordinary diet of their own country, as we are informed by *Kramer*. The seamen

1 Dragoons were originally a class of mounted infantry, who used horses for mobility, but dismounted to fight on foot. From the early 17th century onward, dragoons were increasingly also employed as conventional cavalry and trained for combat with swords and firearms from horseback.
<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dragon>

in the *Channel* cruisers had the very same provision as other ships who went upon different stations: yet it is evident one cause in both places was the diet; as a different diet prevented the disease, and change of diet quickly cured it.

Now, there must have been a quality in the air of *Hungary* different from that of *Bohemia*; something which rendered a diet harmless in the one country, hurtful in the other. The indisposition of the air in *Hungary* was very obvious. The disease prevailed only in the spring, and during a wet season; was much more violent in some parts of the country than in others. *Kramer* enumerates the different places where it raged most, *viz.* where-ever the soil was damp and marshy. This observation has been made not only in *Hungary*, but in other parts of the world.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/78/mode/2up>

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Dr. Cockhurn. — The Doctor's judgment is fully confirmed by experience. We find the college of physicians at *Vienna* sent to *Hungary* great quantities of the most approved antiscorbutic herbs dried in this manner; which were found to be of no benefit. Many of these would have their virtues as little impaired by drying as spinage, e.g. marsh trefoil. *Kramer* tried almost every species of dried herbs to no purpose. Vid. part 3. chap. 2.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/142/mode/2up>

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And if people had been less assiduous in finding out new remedies, and trusted more to the efficacy of these fruits, for preventing this fatal pestilence to seamen, the lives of many thousand sailors, and others², (especially

2 Vid. *Kramer's* observations, part 3. chap. 2. the best ever made on this disease; which abundantly confirm all that is here advanced. In a book published afterwards he makes the following remarks. The scurvy is the most loathsome disease in nature; for which no cure is to be found in your medicine chest, nor in the best-furnished apothecary's shop. Pharmacy gives no relief, surgery as little. Beware of bleeding; shun mercury as a poison: you may rub the gums, you may grease the rigid tendons in the ham, to little purpose. But if you can get green vegetables; if you can prepare a sufficient quantity of the fresh noble antiscorbutic juices; if you have oranges, lemons, or citrons; or their pulp and juice preserved with sugar in casks, so that you can make a lemonade, or rather give to the quantity of three or four ounces of their juice in whey, you will, without other assistance, cure this dreadful evil. *Krameri medicina castrensis.*

during the last war) might in all probability have been preserved.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/158/mode/2up>

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The *Dutch* sailors are said to be less liable to the scurvy than the *English*, owing to this pickled vegetable carried to sea. *Vid. Kramerii epistolam de scorbuto.*

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/172/mode/2up>

p.236-237

If it be said, That scurvy-grass, cresses, and other acrid alcalescent plants, are found highly antiscorbutic; it must likewise be remembered, that they are not perhaps altogether so efficacious as the acescent fruits; or at least become much more so by the addition of lemon-juice, oranges, or a little sorrel; which last the *Greenlanders* are taught by experience to join with them for their cure: these herbs not only strengthen the tone of the stomach and invigorate the organs of digestion, but restore the suppressed perspiration, promote a copious flow of urine, and encrease every secretion in the body, which is the most essential quality of an antiscorbutic composition. That they strengthen the powers of digestion appears not only from the quick increase of appetite occasioned by them, but from the belchings of wind which frequently follow each dose.³

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/236/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/158/mode/2up>

³ *Kramer* observed, that in a thousand patients he had cured by the juices of scurvy-grass and cresses, each dose of the juices occasioned prodigious belchings and wind. It was so uncommon, that he imagined it proceeded from the active and volatile salts of the herbs set loose in the stomach; to which he ascribed their cure. He therefore strictly enjoined his patients, to prevent as much as possible these salts from making their escape in this way.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/236/mode/2up>

Baron JH. Sailors' scurvy before and after James Lind – a reassessment.
Nutr Rev. 2009 Jun;67(6):315-32.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1753-4887.2009.00205.x>

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Some academic dissertations did formulate a unitary etiology, and thus a rational and successful therapy. In 1721, Johann **Kramer**, physician to the Hungarian army, advised “Seek the cure of scurvy neither in the armamentarium of the physician nor in the apothecary shops ... On the other hand, employ fresh vegetables, the juice of fresh antiscorbutic plants, oranges and lemons or the juice of those fruits preserved in sugar; in this way without other means you will be able to overcome this terrible disease.”

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In his chronological abstracts, Lind clearly stated **Kramer** and Bachstrom's unitary fresh vegetables hypothesis for cause and cure of scurvy. However, his own chapters on the causes and cures of scurvy are full of obscure and uncritical concepts, and one is left with his ideas that sea scurvy was due to excess perspiration, could be prevented by ventilation, and that many remedies could be used as well as citrus fruits and cresses.

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It is remarkable in the many descriptions of privations, both at land and sea, characteristic specific clinical features are recognizable today as those of scurvy, and only rarely of other diseases such as those caused by deficiencies of other vitamins (A, B, etc). Indeed, Lind cited the statements of other highly experienced clinicians. **Kramer**, who had seen more than a thousand cases in Hungary, wrote: “The appearances all are constantly uniform”... Moreover, most of those diagnosed then with scurvy responded rapidly, within hours or days, when given what we now know to be effective antiscorbutics, unlike the slower responses to treatments of other known avitaminoses.

Chick H. Early Investigations of Scurvy and the Antiscorbutic Vitamin.
Proceedings of the Nutrition Society. 1953;12(3):210-219.
<https://doi.org/10.1079/PNS19530050>

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Kramer (1720, 1737), early in the eighteenth century, when chief surgeon with the Austrian army in Hungary in the Turkish War and confronted with scurvy among his troops, received from Vienna in response to his appeals for help, a large and varied supply of dried ‘antiscorbutic’ herbs. They proved useless and thousands perished. The incident was in due course forgotten and is yet another example of the way in which many conclusive facts concerning the cause and cure of scurvy were continually set aside with tragic consequences.

Glen King C. The Discovery and Chemistry of Vitamin C.
Proceedings of the Nutrition Society. 1953;12(3):219-227.
<https://doi.org/10.1079/PNS19530051>

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Despite the excellent report on protective foods by **Kramer** (1721, 1737), and Budd's (1841) clear suggestion that chemists would soon isolate the antiscorbutic substance ('essential element') from natural products, a key required for progress was not forged until Holst & Frolich (1907, 1912) reported their use of the guineapig as a means of measuring the nutrient that vanished so easily.

Stockman R. James Lind and Scurvy. Edinb Med J. 1926;33(6):329-350.
<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC5302666>

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On the Continent, **Kramer**, who had been a military surgeon in the Austrian-Turkish War of 1715, wrote of it very well from extensive first-hand knowledge, asserting emphatically that it is not the disease described by Eugalenus.

Hess AF. Scurvy, Past and Present, 1920.
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/40505>
<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7mfk27h>

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"We find the College of Physicians at Vienna sent to Hungary great quantities of the most approved antiscorbutic herbs dried in this manner; which were found to be of no benefit. Many of these would have their virtues as little impaired by drying as spinage, e.g., marsh trefoil. **Kramer** tried almost every species of dried herbs to no purpose." (Treatise on The Scurvy. James Lind, London, 1772, p. 143.)

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"Seek the cure of scurvy neither in the armamentarium of the physician nor in the apothecary shops. The druggist will be of as little aid to you as the art of the surgeon. On the other hand, employ fresh vegetables, the juice of fresh antiscorbutic plants, oranges and lemons or the juice of those fruits preserved with sugar; in this way without other means you will be able to overcome this terrible disease." This reads like the advice of some modern therapist; it is, however, the conclusion of a physician (**Kramer**) who wrote on scurvy almost two hundred years ago, and shows that the treatment of scurvy has undergone no fundamental change in the intervening years. Our resources, however, have been amplified by an increased knowledge of the relative value of antiscorbutic foodstuffs and by the introduction of some new ones.

The text on the following pages is the summary by Lind (1772, 3rd ed.) p.409-419.

<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/408/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/b30511902/page/408/mode/2up>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=ucm.5320216006&seq=433>

<https://hdl.handle.net/2027/ucm.5320216006>

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7fpbavt/items?canvas=431>

The original in Latin:

Jo. Geo. Henrici Kramerii dissertatio epistolica de scorbuto.

<https://books.google.com/books?id=DgteAAAAcAAJ>

<https://books.google.com/books?id=19OM0QEACAAJ>

<https://books.google.com/books?id=mnd0vwEACAAJ>

1737. 1720.

Geo. Henrici Kramerii

dissertatio epistolica de scorbuto.

The case of the Imperial troops in Hungary; transmitted in a letter to the college of physicians in Vienna, by the author.

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The calamity which afflicts the Imperial troops, is not that species of scurvy described by *Eugalenus* and others. It differs from it in three particulars.

1st, It is not infectious. No officers are seized with it; and only the regiments of such nations as use too gross diet. 2dly, It is not a primary, but a secondary disease. It attacks only those who have recovered from fevers, and especially such as have had frequent relapses. 3dly, It is not attended with the many symptoms described by those authors. The appearances in all are constantly uniform, and as follow.

In the first stage the gums are swelled; they are apt to bleed, and stained with livid spots. Upon which ensue great putrefaction, a most offensive stench from the mouth, and a falling out of the teeth.

In the second stage or degree of the malady, there is for the most part a contraction of the joint of the knee, so that the patient cannot extend his leg. Violent shooting pains are felt in this joint, as like-

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wise often in the other joints of the body. The contracted knees are also swelled, with incredible pain and *rigor* of the tendons; and the skin is covered with bluish stains interspersed with small miliary eruptions. In one night's time the eyes, and even other parts of the body, become covered with large livid spots, as if the patient had

received several bruises. These spots are altogether without pain. The muscles of the legs, thighs, and even cheeks, become greatly swelled, and hard, nay altogether indurated. But those swellings, as also the large stains, never suppurate. The pulse is quick, small, and hard; the urine red, with a thick unequal sediment.

If the patient still continues to use an improper diet, as is the case of many of our common soldiers from want of necessaries in *Hungary*, the malady advances to its third stage. The gums become prodigiously swelled, together with the cheeks. A mortification, or *caries* of the jaw, ensues; both which prove incurable. The difficulty of breathing is so great, that the patients not only faint away upon the slightest motion of the body; but frequently, when walking about, drop down suddenly dead. They generally complain excessively of this difficulty of breathing a few days before death, though they have neither cough nor spitting. All the species of dropsies⁴, and watery swellings on the body, accompany

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the advanced stages of this calamity; in so much that, by lying with the head in a declining posture, the face in half an hour becomes so swelled, that the person cannot open his eyes. Such swellings often disappear and return. They are subject to profuse bleedings at the nose; and, in these deplorable circumstances, to a purging with frequent discharges of blood by stool, which often closes the scene. In the beginning of the disease, the appetite and thirst are natural; but towards the close of the malady, the appetite fails and the thirst is increased. Of the many other symptoms described in this disease by authors, none else occur but those alone

4 Dropsy.

The historical diagnosis of dropsy – which is now obsolete – indicated simply an abnormal accumulation of fluid. The word derives from the Greek *hydrops* (water). Alternative or supplementary terms included *hydrothorax* (fluid in the chest cavity), *ascites* (which still indicates excess free fluid in the abdominal cavity), *anasarca* (still used to describe generalized edema throughout the body).

<https://doi.org/10.1017/CHOL9780521332866.101>

An ancient medical term used to indicate different conditions including chronic heart failure.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcard.2017.07.104>

Scurvy can cause heart failure, eg.

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s12890-024-02941-x> <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC10949735>

which have been mentioned.

This is the fatal mischief which destroys many of our people in *Hungary*, at farthest in the space of two or three months, but for the most part in three or four weeks. If the patient survives until summer, he either perfectly recovers, or remains incurably contracted.

The causes of this evil are, frequent relapses after fevers, which have been epidemic in the country; the moist and marshy soil; but especially gross and viscid diet, viz. flesh and the grosser farines, coarse heavy bread, and pudding (or a food called *rollatschen*) eaten by the *Bohemians* more than by all others. They are indeed al-

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most the only nation who suffer. One thing remarkable is, that this disease does not appear in *Hungary* in summer, autumn, nor in winter; but every year in the beginning of spring.

I come now to what has been attempted, both by myself and others, towards the cure: and must first observe, that 400 of the troops near *Belgrade* having taken mercury without my advice, the dreadful consequence was, they all died in a salivation! Shunning therefore that fatal drug, I generally at first gave a vomit, in order to cleanse the stomach, and so to procure a more certain entrance of the specific antiscorbutics, with their full virtues, into the blood. I then administered, in every form that could be thought of, or that has been recommended by authors, the most approved antiscorbutic remedies⁵; but, alas, all was in vain!

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In a word, there is nothing that has been recommended by the best classical and standard authors⁶, which I have not made trial of, except the juices of the fresh green plants, and their quintessence recommended by *May*⁷: It not being in my power to

procure those herbs, or their juices; because, as I observed before, they do not grow in this country. We have nothing here but wild rocket and wild mustard; but even of these, who can gather a sufficient quantity for such a number of the distressed? Milk, were it proper, cannot be purchased for so great a multitude of people: and the same may be said of whey.

After having met with such melancholy disappointments, in the trial of what has been recommended by others, and whatever I could think of myself; reflecting that tedious fevers had generally preceded, and that a slow fever still accompanied the disease, I had recourse to the *cort. peruv.* given in the form either of electuary or infusion. By this, in a few days, I formerly cured sixty soldiers in the regiment of *Bagnan*, who were in the second stage of

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the disease. It is now two years since: but at the same time they had a proper diet, and such food as cannot at this time be procured. I have already tried mustard-seed, which is said to have saved the besieged garrison of *Rochelle*, when over-run with this disease; but here, like all other remedies, it is of no efficacy. I need not say any thing of external applications: as such powerful internal helps do not avail, little can be expected from them. I shall only observe, that different regiments have used the baths of the country; but all to no purpose.

I therefore humbly request, that if any of you, gentlemen, be possessed of an *arcanum*, or a remedy that may overcome this *Herculean* disease, you will favour me with it; as also your best advice. Perhaps some of you may have the knowledge of the fixed mercury boasted of by *Dolæus* and *Helmont*, which will cure the scurvy without

5 ... I have also given salts of every kind, volatile and fixed, particularly ...

In place of the juice of citrons and lemons, which cannot be got here, I gave *acet. theriac.* or vinegar, in which many of the before-mentioned ingredients, particularly the celebrated *rad. armoraciae*, were infused. I was not sparing of the most costly medicines, *tinct. mart. antimonii, luna helvet. &c.*

6 Here he enumerates sixteen modern writers on the scurvy, of the greatest repute, with an &c.

7 A medicine of Dr. *Michael's*. Vid. p. 141. The author afterwards observes, that it was of no efficacy. [p.141: ... Dr. *Michael*, a very great chemist, who was the first university professor of chemistry in Europe; and remitted him a considerable sum of money, in order to bear the expence of his experiments, with

the aid of such a proper diet as cannot at this time be procured for the wretched sufferers in *Hungary*.

A copy of this melancholy case of the troops was delivered to each member of the college of physicians in *Vienna*; and, by order of the Dean of Faculty, all were desired in three days time to give in their opinion in writing. Which produced the following answer.

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We have received your very accurate account of the scurvy, which commits such dreadful havock among the Imperial troops during the spring in *Hungary*; and it is ordered directly to be printed. After having had all circumstances duly weighed by the most experienced of our faculty, the first rule we prescribe, is great attention to the *nonnaturals*. Without this, the most excellent medicines may fail; but when a proper regard is had to these, simple remedies will do great things. As the sources of this calamity seem to be impure air, and an unwholesome marshy soil (evils not easily remedied); the troops must often shift their quarters, and remove into a better air. When in unhealthful stations, they are, by way of prevention, to use the smoak of tobacco, juniper, &c. They should have always dry straw to lay upon the ground; and as wholesome food as can be procured for them.

As to the cure (after noting with infamy those who have recommended a mercurial salivation in this disease, as more properly destroyers of the human race than physicians) we would advise a gentle vomit of *ipecacuan* to be premised; and afterwards the approved antiscorbutics of the vegetable kind to be given, viz. scurvygrass, brooklime, cresses, fumitory,⁸ *St. John's wort*, marsh-trefoil, &c. The juice, extract, tincture, decoction, &c. of these,

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may be administered either in whey or broth. As you have none of those plants, we have sent you their seeds to be sown in the country; and until such time as they grow up, have supplied you with a quantity of the dried herbs, and of their inspissated juices. Besides which, we would recommend two remedies of great and experienced virtues⁹.

The author's farther explanations and experience in this disease.

The scurvy attacked only those who, after frequent relapses, and a recovery from fevers, used a crude viscid diet. Hence not one officer was seized with it; nor even any of the common men among the dragoons, as their pay and living were better. It was always accompanied with remains of the fever in the pulse and urine. Both in *Hungary* and in *Piedmont*, where the troops were lately afflicted with it, the natives were at the same time altogether exempted from it. The disease occurs oftentimes in *Germany*, among such people as live altogether on the boiled pulses, without eating any green vegetables or summer-fruits. In

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the hospital at *Dresden* there are scorbutic patients every year. It is often a fatal mischief in besieged towns, as also to seamen in long voyages. It is, however, quickly cured in cold countries; as in *Greenland*, by scurvygrass; and in warmer countries, by the juice of oranges. Dutch sailors effectually prevent this distress, by eating once or twice a-week pickled cabbage. When blood was injudiciously drawn for relief of the scorbutic asthma, there was no separation of the watery part: it was covered a-top with a white greasy film. The contraction occurs in no other joint but the knee. The disease constantly begins, and regularly advances, in the man-

a promise of a much greater, in case he succeeded in the discovery of a remedy for prevention of the scurvy at sea. The Doctor spent an incredible deal of time and labour in preparing the most elaborated chemical medicines...]

8 Fumaria, fumitory.

<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Fumaria>

9 The one a paste of *pulv. rad. chin. sarsaparil. et hordei*, from *Hoferus*; the other, a distilled antiscorbutic water, from *Zwingerus*. The author afterwards observes they were of no efficacy.

ner as described in the relation transmitted to the college. No person can be supposed to labour under the scurvy, or any symptom of it, unless the gums are affected. Putrefaction of the gums is the primary and inseparable symptom of the malady in its very first stage. A great difficulty of breathing, dropsy, and dysentery, attending the last stage, render the case often incurable. As to scorbutic pains, it is remarkable they afflict equally both day and night, and are not increased by heat, or by lying in bed. The knees, when swelled, are generally covered with large effusions of blood under the skin. These never come to suppuration on any part of the body, except

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cept on the gums, where they often break and ulcerate. The flexor tendons of the legs alone become rigid, viz. the tendons of the *seminervosus* and *semimembranosus* muscles. Colics afflict in this disease when there is a *diarrhæa* or dysentery, but never otherwise. In many thousand scorbutic patients, I never once saw the true pleurisy, nephritic pains, strangury¹⁰, nor bleedings from the skin, except where there was a wound; although scorbutic people are subject to discharges of blood from the lungs, stomach, intestines, &c.; nor did I ever observe any other ulcers than what have been described, in the gums and cheeks,

much less any species whatever of a *scabies*. Scorbutic persons are never afflicted with epileptic fits, palsies, tremors, &c. Their death is for the most part tranquil, if you except their laborious breathing.

I can aver from experience in above a thousand cases, that this malady is most effectually cured by the fresh juice of scurvy-grass and cresses, either mixed or separately, taken to the quantity of three ounces twice or thrice a-day in warm broth. These juices occasion slight flushings of the face, are carminative, and promote urine and perspiration. As those herbs cannot be obtained fresh in many parts of *Hungary*, nor in warm climates, the disease may be effectually cured by three or four ounces of

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the juice of oranges or citrons, taken twice a-day in a pint of water with sugar, or rather in whey. By juice of citron in whey, twenty patients were lately cured in the hospital of St. *Mark* at *Vienna*. As to a preservative medicine against it, I know of none but the tincture of the *Peruvian* bark, taken at bed-time to the quantity of two *drachms*, either by itself, or mixed with other bitters. By this remedy the famous Count *Bonneval* preserved himself and his domestics, many years in *Hungary*, free from the distempers of the country.

10 Strangury. The symptom characterized by painful, frequent urination of small volumes that are expelled slowly only by straining; a slow and painful spasmodic discharge of urine drop by drop